

Data Collection and Enrichment Tool v3

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Contents

1. Introduction	5
2. Overview of data sources	6
3. Exposure metrics and data enrichments	7
4. Measuring the physical environment	10
4.1 Street design features and physical layout	10
4.1.1 Pedestrian and bicycling infrastructure	10
4.1.2 Examples	10
4.1.3 Guidelines	10
4.2 Street network metrics	12
4.2.1 Betweenness centrality	13
4.2.2 Intersection closeness centrality	13
4.2.3 Sinuosity	13
4.2.4 Examples	14
4.2.5 Guidelines	17
4.3 Spatial accessibility	17
4.3.1 Different spatial accessibility measures	17
4.3.2 Pedestrian walksheds	18
4.3.3 Examples	19
4.3.4 Guidelines	20
4.4 Access to amenities	20
4.4.1 Euclidean buffers	21
4.4.2 Pedestrian walksheds	21
4.4.3 Co-accessibility index	21
4.4.4 Examples	23
4.4.5 Guidelines	25
4.5 Access to greenspaces	25
4.5.1 Euclidean buffers	26
4.5.2 Pedestrian walksheds	26
	3

4.5.3 Access on the move	29
4.5.4 Examples	31
4.5.5 Guidelines	33
4.6 Access to playgrounds	33
4.6.1 Euclidean buffers	34
4.6.2 Pedestrian walksheds	34
4.6.3 Children's play-space metric	34
4.6.4 Examples	35
4.6.5 Guidelines	38
4.7 Perceived attributes of the physical environment	38
4.7.1 Crowdsourcing perceptions of the built environment	38
4.7.2 Perceived safety	39
4.7.3 Perceived attractiveness	43
4.7.4 Perceptions of greenspaces	46
4.7.5 Guidelines	48
5. Conclusion	48
References	49

1. Introduction

Measuring the physical environment is crucial to determining the degree of exposure, assessing health and well-being outcomes, and achieving local and global health and sustainability goals. Effective health policy and planning interventions necessitate evidence-informed quantifiable targets and standards that can be measured consistently across different geographical contexts. The Data Collection and Enrichment Tool provides a number of methodologies for measuring physical environment features that have been shown to have the greatest impact on human health, both physical and mental. A unique characteristic of this tool is that it offers comprehensive ways of consistently measuring physical environment features that account for both environmental and experiential/perceptual qualities. To ensure that the definition of physical environment features and the related data collection is robust and consistent across different geographical contexts, we strive to use data sources with global coverage, such as OpenStreetMap (OSM) and the EU's Global Human Settlement Data (see Sect. 2 of this document, and a more detailed description in Deliverable 5.8). This also allows for comparing exposures to various physical environment features across different geographical contexts within and between cities.

The metrics that comprise the tool were either created from scratch or extended from existing ones to capture the wide range of physical environment characteristics in a scalable manner. In this document, we first describe the methods for capturing and measuring design and physical layout features before progressing to measuring subjective perceptions and experiential qualities of the physical environment. We begin by measuring the street layout, in terms of morphology, available pavement/sidewalk space, and bicycling infrastructure. These characteristics are critical for more accessible streets that prioritise active transportation over car use. We then provide methods for measuring street connectivity. This is necessary not only for accessibility but also for creating more vibrant streets that encourage social interaction. Following that, we describe various methods for measuring spatial accessibility, emphasising their strengths and weaknesses. This is made more explicit by measuring access to amenities, greenspaces, playgrounds, and the co-accessibility of different age groups. Finally, we present a set of methodologies for capturing experiential factors of the physical environment, which, despite their importance, are rarely considered by any walkability or accessibility scores due to their subjective nature, difficulty in quantifying, and limited data availability at larger spatial extents.

Each of the presented methods is illustrated by examples and supported by guidelines that ensure consistent measurement and, thus, comparability, to facilitate the adoption of our tool within and beyond Equal-Life. Of course, there are various methods for measuring the physical environment, each with its own set of values and limitations. Some factors may weigh more heavily than others depending on the mechanisms of interest or the scale of proposed interventions (e.g., in the case of local air quality, proximity to green spaces could be more important than access or actual usage of these spaces). Identifying what measures are needed and where they are needed, as well as weighing factors, requires expertise from various scientific and professional fields. Nonetheless, the methodologies presented here provide a robust and consistent way of measuring the physical environment across different geographical contexts. Each measurement methodology included in the tool comes with open-source code detailed in Deliverable 5.8. The metrics presented in this document can be combined with other

metrics and models described in other deliverables (e.g., noise, air pollution, vegetation index, traffic).

2. Overview of data sources

To enable consistent local and global comparative analyses, open data that are robust and have at least a city-wide or, where available, global coverage are required. For this reason, the Data Collection and Enrichment Tool framework prioritises data consistency and coverage over locally available datasets that, while more detailed, impede analyses across different geographical contexts.

We use OpenStreetMap (OSM), a crowd-sourced mapping platform that is publicly available, for the majority of the metrics in the tool. OSM contains data at a high granularity, and its completeness is ever-increasing (Barrington-Leigh & Millard-Ball, 2017). It is a valuable source of urban morphology and land use data and its expanding coverage allows us to replicate our enrichment methods in any of the cohorts and school study areas. OSM is updated and coded on a regular basis in accordance with consistent and community-led guidelines (Boeing, 2021). Its well-documented taxonomy¹ also ensures that the physical environment features are defined consistently across the different study areas. Moreover, it is possible to use OSM data from previous years, starting from September 30, 2012. It should be noted, however, that the completeness of OSM has fluctuated over time. In other words, every year, users add content and enrich the map. Thus, while a neighbourhood's physical representation may not have changed significantly in reality over time (for example, in terms of how many streets it has or how well these streets are connected), its digital representation will have changed as it becomes more and more complete.

In some of the example cases presented in this document, we extended OSM data with more nuanced local open datasets. Examples include detailed land use data from the Dutch Basisregistratie Grootschalige Topografie (BGT) and population data from the Dutch Central Bureau for Statistics (CBS), used in capturing street infrastructure (see Sect. 4.1.2) and aspects of access on the move (see Sect. 4.5.3) and the co-accessibility index (see Sect. 4.4.3). This was done to demonstrate the level of detail that some of our metrics can capture if detailed open datasets are available. Oftentimes, tradeoffs must be made between the completeness and consistency of the available data. However, even if the data source feeding the metrics is not the most complete (as is the case with OSM), the measurement capacity of the metrics comprising the tool is unaffected.

We rely on street-level imagery to extract experiential and perceptual environmental qualities, which gives a fresh perspective on how we represent the physical environment. Street-level imagery simulates the process of a person walking down the street, providing a three-dimensional overview of visible spatial elements (e.g., building facades, trees, street furniture). Subjective perceptions of the physical environment such as perceived safety and attractiveness are often difficult to quantify across large spatial extents in a robust and comprehensive manner. To measure city-wide perceptions of physical environment features, we strive to develop reliable and, to the greatest extent possible, reproducible crowdsourcing methodologies (see Sect. 4.7.1

¹ https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Map_features (accessed 23 February 2023).

– 4.7.4). A more comprehensive description of the data sources used is provided in Sect. 2 of Deliverable 5.8.

3. Exposure metrics and data enrichments

Table 1 summarises the definitions of the metrics and physical environment features captured by the Data Collection and Enrichment Tool.

Table 1. Definitions of the metrics and physical environment features captured by the Data Collection and Enrichment tool.

Metric	Definition	Captured features
Sidewalk space	Average width of each sidewalk calculated as the street space (polygon) perpendicular to each street's centreline within the sidewalk's boundaries. The sidewalk width for each street segment is calculated by taking the average width of all sidewalks within 10m of the street segment and normalising it by the sum of the corresponding sidewalk lengths (see Sect. 4.1).	Street design & layout
Cycling space	Average width of each bicycle path calculated as the street space (polygon) perpendicular to each street's centreline within the bicycle path's boundaries. The bicycle path width for each street segment is calculated by taking the average width of all bicycle paths within 10m of the street segment and normalising it by the sum of the corresponding bicycle path lengths (see Sect. 4.1).	Street design & layout
Betweenness centrality	A street connectivity indicator for the streets that are most frequently used when attempting to follow the shortest route to reach each street intersection from all other streets. It is often used to estimate the number of pedestrians passing by a given street or the potential traffic volume (see Sect. 4.2.1).	Street connectivity
Intersection closeness centrality	A street connectivity indicator that reflects the distance travelled from one street intersection to all others. Street intersections with higher values are the ones from which all other intersections can be reached more efficiently in terms of distance (see Sect. 4.2.2).	Street connectivity
Sinuosity	A street layout indicator that reflects the straightness of a street segment by quantifying how much longer it is relative to a straight line between its start and end points. A line's sinuosity is defined as the ratio of its curvilinear length and its Euclidean distance (i.e., straight line) (see Sect. 4.2.3).	Street layout
Spatial accessibility (spatial buffer)	The spatial buffer approach to measuring accessibility employs circular buffers (else referred to as Euclidean buffers because of the straight-line radius used in defining the buffer zones) around the centroid of the polygon delineating origin locations (e.g., homes or schools) to define whether a given amenity is accessible. Points of interest (e.g., amenities such as parks and playgrounds) located within a specified radius are considered accessible. This method does not consider the street networks and any other access barriers (see Sect. 4.3.1).	Accessibility, walkability
Spatial accessibility (pedestrian walkshed)	The pedestrian walkshed approach to measuring accessibility employs varying buffers around the centroid of the polygon delineating origin locations (e.g., homes or schools) corresponding to various travel time distances (e.g., 5, 10, or 15-minute walks) along the pedestrian road network. A walkshed encompasses the area that can be reached within walking distance from any given origin location. Points of interest (e.g., amenities such as parks and playgrounds) located within the pedestrian walkshed are considered accessible to pedestrians. This method takes into account the street network and — sometimes — other access barriers (see Sect. 4.3.2).	Accessibility, walkability
Spatial accessibility (patronage betweenness)	The patronage betweenness approach to measuring accessibility estimates flows of pedestrians on the move from one location (e.g., home or school) to another (e.g., a park or a playground) while accounting for typical pedestrian behaviour. As such, patronage betweenness is used as an accessibility measure on the assumption that people who pass by a location are more likely to visit it because they do not have to make a separate trip (see Sect. 4.5.3).	Accessibility, walkability

Metric	Definition	Captured features
Co-accessibility	The co-accessibility index indicates how accessible a given location is to people of different age groups. It approximates how people of different ages occupy the same location and, as a result, serves as a proxy for potential encounters and intergenerational interactions by estimating the degree to which different age groups have access to the same locations (see Sect. 4.4.3).	Social cohesion/segregation
Access to greenspace (spatial buffers, walksheds, on the move)	Similar to the spatial buffer, pedestrian walkshed, and patronage betweenness approaches to measuring spatial accessibility, but specifically for greenspaces. Buffers and walksheds are calculated around children's homes or schools. The patronage betweenness approach captures how children are exposed to greenspaces on a daily basis, such as while walking from home to school without making a separate trip, as long as their commuting path passes through vegetated areas (see Sect. 4.5).	Greenspace exposure
Access to playgrounds (spatial buffers, walksheds, children's play-space metric)	The spatial buffer and pedestrian walkshed approaches to measuring spatial accessibility are all applicable to playgrounds too. The children's play-space metric calculates the ease with which children can reach places for play, which takes into account barriers along routes such as main traffic infrastructure and water bodies that cannot be safely crossed via pedestrian tunnels or bridges, as well as the inner parts of large greenspaces where natural surveillance may be lacking (see Sect. 4.6).	Playability, walkability
Perceived safety	A subjective indicator of the sense of safety. Natural surveillance, or "eyes on the street" from overlooking buildings, serves as a proxy for perceived safety. The measurement of natural surveillance involves the calculation of sightlines from the windows to each street and vice versa, as well as the windows of surrounding buildings. Two types of surveillance are calculated for each street segment: (1) street surveillance, which captures the surveillance of windows from the street level and vice versa, and (2) occupant surveillance, which captures the surveillance of windows from surrounding buildings (see Sect. 4.7.2).	Experiential qualities of a place
Perceived attractiveness	A subjective indicator of how appealing and welcoming the physical environment feels. Crowdsourcing and street-level imagery are employed to capture how different elements of the physical environment contribute to its perceived attractiveness (e.g., greenery, the density and mix of land use along streets, the morphology and aesthetics of buildings, intersection density, good visibility and street lighting, and the quality and maintenance of sidewalks) (see Sect. 4.7.3).	Experiential qualities of a place
Perceived greenspaces	A crowdsourced indicator of people's perceptions of various greenspaces and planned activity visits. Greenspace perceptions may differ from those represented on official land cover and land use maps or by NDVI indexes (see Sect. 4.7.4).	Experiential qualities of a place

4. Measuring the physical environment

4.1 Street design features and physical layout

A growing body of evidence has highlighted the importance of street design and physical layout features such as connectivity and infrastructure quality in making streets more accessible and welcoming, thereby promoting active travel among children and adults (van Holle et al., 2012; Hooper et al., 2015; Cerin et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2017). Aside from the morphology (i.e., geometrical features pertaining to the shape of the available pavement/sidewalk space) and layout (i.e., topological features such as connectivity) of the streetscape, another important aspect of streets is the amount of space allocated to active modes of transportation, namely, walking and biking. The geometrical (i.e., length, sinuosity), topological (i.e., betweenness, intersection closeness), and infrastructural (i.e., sidewalks, bike paths) features of streets work together to determine how connected different places and neighbourhoods are and, as a result, shape the degree of walkability and bike-ability.

We developed several methodologies in the data collection and enrichment tool to query geospatial data about streets from OSM and to capture streetscape infrastructure for walking (i.e., sidewalk coverage) and bicycling (i.e., bikeable paths). The collected data can then be used to calculate walksheds and bikesheds (i.e., network distance buffers around specific locations that can be covered by pedestrians or cyclists within a given time window), which are essential in accessibility analyses (see also Sect. 4.3 – 4.6).

4.1.1 Pedestrian and bicycling infrastructure

To calculate the average width of sidewalks, we extend a method that Harvey (2020) originally developed for classifying urban streets based on their average pavement/sidewalk space. A similar strategy is used for bike paths. Here we use the city centre of Amsterdam, the Netherlands, to showcase the implementation of our methodology. In addition to OSM data, we further extract, at a granular level, streets (polygons) where pedestrians and cyclists have priority from the Dutch land use dataset Basisregistratie Grootschalige Topografie (BGT), which covers the entire territory of the Netherlands (Kadaster, 2020). We compute the average width of each sidewalk (or bicycle path) by calculating the street space that is perpendicular to each street's centreline within the sidewalk's (or bicycle path's) boundaries.² The sidewalk width for each street segment is then calculated by taking the average width of all sidewalks within 10m of the street segment and normalising it by the sum of the corresponding sidewalk lengths.

4.1.2 Examples

Fig. 1 depicts the resulting classification of Amsterdam's street infrastructure based on the width of available sidewalks (bottom left) and bike paths (bottom right). Grey-coloured segments denote streets where there is no sidewalk or bike path nearby. This appears to be the case in Amsterdam's historical city centre neighbourhoods (e.g., Jordaan, Wallen), distinguished by narrow sidewalks and a lack of bike paths. Given the granular datasets covering the entire country on BGT, this analysis can be easily replicated in other Dutch cities. If highly granular polygon geospatial datasets about the street network are available, it is possible to replicate our

² The centre lines of each sidewalk polygon are calculated. This may result in one or more consecutive lines representing different parts of the sidewalk, depending on the complexity of the sidewalk shape.

methodology for cohort addresses in countries other than The Netherlands (see also Sect. 4.1.3).

Figure 1. Pedestrian and bicycle infrastructure in Amsterdam's Centrum district. Pedestrian network (top left), bicycle network (top right), pedestrian network enriched and classified by average sidewalk width (bottom left), and bicycle network enriched and classified by average bike lane width (bottom right).

4.1.3 Guidelines

- **Data**
 - **Area of interest:** Decide on a city or neighbourhood area of interest. Road width calculations are computationally heavy, so do not choose an area larger than necessary.
 - **Street network:** Obtain a street network dataset, for example from [OpenStreetMap](#) and use its segment attributes (i.e., tags, easily done through the Python package [OSMnx](#)) to filter out the pedestrian and bicycle infrastructure.
 - **Road surface polygons:** Optionally, if available, obtain a local dataset with polygon geometries (i.e., areas, not just lines, see for example the [Dutch BGT](#)) for each and every pedestrian (e.g., sidewalks, pedestrian areas) and/or bicycle road surface (e.g., bike lanes).
- **Process**
 - Visualise the two street networks. Optionally, you can use tags to explore differences in characteristics such as pavement type and the presence of sidewalks. Note that these tags are not always present and therefore information may not be complete.
 - If you have road surface polygons, determine the widths of the geometries using the modified Harvey (2020) method and visualise results either per polygon or aggregated per street network road segment (see the Dutch [Social Distancing Dashboard](#), developed by TUD | Urban Analytics).
- **Software**
 - We use Python code to collect and filter data, and to calculate widths of geometries. Our code uses, among others, the [OSMnx](#) library (Boeing, 2017). Detailed instructions for installing and running the code for these metrics appear in Sect. 4.2.1 of Deliverable 5.8.

4.2 Street network metrics

City streets account for most outdoor public spaces (UN-Habitat, 2013). They are, in fact, the most fundamental component of a city's built environment and spatial structure. The structure and configuration of the street network, among other core aspects of the physical environment, can promote or hinder mobility, accessibility, walkability, connectivity, and social interactions and influence feelings of (un)safety. Streets facilitate access to basic services, amenities, and recreation areas. At the same time, they are potential sources of exposure to various outdoor factors (e.g., noise and air pollution). As a result, understanding the design and structure of the street network is critical for assessing people's well-being and quality of life, particularly children's.

The street network analysis incorporates a number of metrics related to street connectivity, sinuosity, centrality, and betweenness. In fields such as urban planning, transportation, geography, and landscape design, various metrics have been developed and used. We developed a number of measurement methodologies to calculate and enrich properties of the city's street network for the purposes of the data collection and enrichment tool.

4.2.1 Betweenness centrality

Every street intersection can be represented as a point in the street network connected to all other street intersections. Betweenness centrality estimates which streets are most frequently used when attempting to follow the shortest route to reach each street intersection from all other streets. It is often used to estimate the number of pedestrians passing by a given street or the potential traffic volume.

To estimate the streets' betweenness centrality (Brandes, 2008), the street network should be represented as a graph, with nodes (n) representing street intersections and edges (e) representing streets. Using this graph, we determine the shortest paths between any two nodes. The number of shortest paths that contain this edge divided by the total number of shortest paths gives the betweenness centrality of an edge, which is given by the following formula:

$$\text{edge betweenness } (e) = \sum_{s,t \in V} \frac{\sigma_{st}(e)}{\sigma_{st}}$$

Where V denotes the set of nodes, σ_{st} is the number of paths from s to t , and $\sigma_{st}(e)$ is the number of shortest paths that contain e (Fig. 2).

4.2.2 Intersection closeness centrality

The closeness centrality of each street intersection reflects the distance travelled from one street intersection to all others. Street intersections with higher values are the ones from which all other intersections can be reached more efficiently in terms of distance. In other words, the closer a street intersection is to all the other street intersections, the more central it is.

To estimate the closeness centrality of street intersections, the street network should be represented as a graph, with nodes (n) representing the street intersections and edges (e) representing streets. The reciprocal of the average of the shortest path between this node and all the other nodes in the graph is the closeness centrality of each node, which is given by the following formula:

$$\text{node closeness } (u) = \frac{n - 1}{\sum_{x=1}^{n-1} d(x, u)}$$

Where $d(x, u)$ is the length of the shortest path between x and u , and $n-1$ is the number of all nodes that are reachable from u (Fig. 3).

4.2.3 Sinuosity

This metric reflects the straightness of a street segment by quantifying how much longer it is relative to a straight line between its start and end points. A line's sinuosity is defined as the ratio of its curvilinear length and its Euclidean distance (i.e., straight line). Sinuosity can range from 1 (i.e., in the case of a straight line) to infinity (Fig. 4).

4.2.4 Examples

Betweenness centrality

Figure 2. Betweenness centrality scores of streets in Barcelona, Stockholm, Amsterdam, and Helsinki.

Intersection closeness centrality

Figure 3. Closeness centrality scores of street intersections in Barcelona, Stockholm, Amsterdam, and Helsinki.

Sinuosity

Barcelona

Stockholm

Amsterdam

Helsinki

Low
sinuosity
(1)

Low-to-medium
sinuosity
(1 - 1.000004)

Medium-to-high
sinuosity
(1.000004 - 1.007)

High
sinuosity
(1.007+)

Figure 4. Sinuosity scores of streets in Barcelona, Stockholm, Amsterdam, and Helsinki.

4.2.5 Guidelines

- **Data**
 - **Area of interest:** Decide on a city or metropolitan area of interest. The number of streets and intersections in the selected area could affect the quality of the results. Selecting areas with a very limited number of streets and street intersections could result in measurements that lack diversity and are not informative.
 - **Street network:** Collect street network data, for example from [OpenStreetMap](#).
- **Process**
 - Ensure your street network is a connected graph. Based on the street network topology, calculate betweenness centrality and intersection closeness.
 - Based on the geometry of each street segment, calculate its sinuosity.
- **Software**
 - We developed the Python Library [ctwalk](#) to support the execution of all the above steps simply by inserting the name of a city or the bounding box that covers the area of your interest. Ctwalk is based on the libraries [NetworkX](#) and [OSMnx](#). Detailed instructions for installing and running the code for these metrics appear in Sect. 4.2.2 of Deliverable 5.8.

4.3 Spatial accessibility

4.3.1 Different spatial accessibility measures

The way we measure accessibility matters. Access to given destinations (e.g., greenspaces or other amenities such as playgrounds) is traditionally evaluated based on the *distribution* of destinations within a given area (e.g., administrative boundaries of a neighbourhood or a city) or by means of circular *buffer zones*, typically surrounding the residential space. Fig. 5 depicts how the selection of different measures affects the assessment of greenspace accessibility. The presented example illustrates the measurement/outcome disparities using the official administrative boundaries of the municipality of Delft. Panel A focuses exclusively on the spatial distribution of greenspaces within the official municipal boundaries. This gives a rough idea of how much greenspace is available per square metre to citizens, assuming equal distribution across the geographic space.

In Panel B, greenspace accessibility is assessed using Euclidean circular buffers of 800m radius (i.e., approximately a 15-minute walk) drawn around the boundaries of each green space. Based on these Euclidean buffer zones, it is estimated that nearly 100% of Delft's population has access to parks within a straight-line 15-minute walk of any location in the city. Finally, in Panel C, greenspace accessibility is assessed using buffer zones around each greenspace, but this time the network distance is taken into account (i.e., the distance/time required to reach a location using the existing street network, rather than straight-line Euclidean distances). In this case, 84% of Delft's residents are estimated to have access to parks within a 15-minute walk. This example demonstrates how different measures influence the analysis' results and can, correspondingly, lead to drawing erroneous conclusions.

Figure 5. Parks larger than 10,000m² within walking distance in Delft, the Netherlands: distribution (A), access using Euclidean buffer zones (B), and access using network buffer zones (C). Only 35 Delft residents (0.0%) are estimated not to have access to green space within a 15-minute walk when using Euclidean buffer zones (B), compared to 16810 residents (16.4%) when using network buffer zones (C).

4.3.2 Pedestrian walksheds

To determine which locations are accessible within walking distance, we calculate different pedestrian walksheds. Walksheds can be calculated in a variety of ways. The most basic and widely used method is to draw circular buffers of varying radii around the centroid (i.e., geometrical centre) of the polygon delineating a point of interest (e.g., a park). Instead, we calculate the walksheds in the following analyses by taking into account the pedestrian road network. We use buffers that correspond to travel time distances of 5, 10, and 15 minutes along the pedestrian road network. In the case of greenspaces, we compute these buffers around any intersection in each greenspace. In this way, the walkshed encompasses the area that can be reached within walking distance from any intersection of roads located within the green space.

In general, there is no consensus in the literature as to which (travel time) distance best captures pedestrian trips. Furthermore, the distance travelled on foot may differ significantly between population age groups. However, evidence suggests that the three aforementioned walksheds account for the vast majority of pedestrian trips (Pushkarev and Zupan, 1975; Guy and Wringley, 1987; Handy and Niemeier, 1997; Zacharias, 2001; Murtagh et al., 2021).

Two ways to define the corresponding radii determine the buffer size. According to Waddell and Ulfarsson (2003), a 5-, 10-, or 15-minute walk corresponds to a network radius of 300m, 500m, or 800m, respectively. The radius can also be calculated using the average walking speed. Even though this varies across population age groups, Schimpl et al. (2011) estimate that the lowest average walking speed is found to be 1.2m/sec (for people over 60 years of age), whereas the highest is 1.29m/sec (for people between 40 and 49 years of age). Murtagh et al. (2021) also estimate an average speed of 1.31m/sec at a self-selected pace among healthy adults. Our primary focus, however, is on children and adolescents. In our case, the longest considered walking trip (i.e., a 15-minute walk or 900sec) corresponds to a (1.29m/sec x 900sec) — (1.2m/sec x 900sec) = 81m (or 99m according to Murtagh et al.'s estimates) difference in

network radius distance between age groups. Given the small distance difference, we calculate walking trips to greenspaces, playgrounds, and other amenities using the average walking speed of 1.26m/sec (i.e., the average of all age groups, as defined by Schimpl et al. (2011)) throughout. Of course, people can travel much longer distances by bike. All of our calculations in this document, however, are based solely on pedestrian walking trips. Bike trips may be included in future analyses if necessary.

4.3.3 Examples

Figure 6. Amenities within a 5-minute (yellow), 10-minute (blue), or 15-minute (purple) walk.

4.3.4 Guidelines

- **Data**
 - **Places:** Obtain a dataset of the places you want to quantify accessibility of (e.g., parks).
 - **Street network:** Optionally, if you want to calculate walksheds, obtain an urban street network dataset as a connected graph, for example from [OpenStreetMap](#) via the [OSMnx](#) library.
 - **Population:** Optionally, obtain a dataset of population statistics, i.e., per neighbourhood, postal code area, or local grid cell (e.g., local data such as by the [Dutch CBS](#)), or houses (e.g., from [OpenStreetMap](#), filtering on building tags).
- **Process**
 - Calculate the count or total land surface of the places. You can divide this number by the population or number of houses in your area of interest, to quantify the availability (rather than accessibility) of places in the area.
 - Generate circular buffer zones around the places. Quantify the total area or, potentially, the population or number of households located within these zones (i.e., having access to the places).
 - Generate walksheds (i.e., network buffer zones) around the places using your street network data set. Quantify the total area or, potentially, the population or number of households located within these walksheds (i.e., having access to the places)
 - You can compare different places with each other in terms of their accessibility to people, or compare between sub-areas to what extent people have access to these places.
- **Software**
 - We use Python code to collect [OpenStreetMap](#) data and to calculate accessibility. Our code uses, among others, the [OSMnx](#) library (Boeing, 2017). Detailed instructions for installing and running the code for these metrics appear in Sect. 4.2.5 of Deliverable 5.8 as additional examples.

4.4 Access to amenities

Access to individual amenities (e.g., playgrounds, sports facilities, health facilities) may influence people's daily habits and activities, and thus their physical and mental health. For instance, easy access to either high or low-quality food stores close to someone's home has been shown to promote or obstruct healthier eating habits and, as a result, people's health (Larson et al., 2009; Moro et al., 2021). Access to a set of amenities may also have an indirect impact on people's well-being. Access to a dense and diverse mix of amenities, for example, could lead to more vibrant neighbourhoods with a stronger sense of community, encourage physical activity through active travel (i.e., people are encouraged to visit multiple venues in a single trip by walking or biking from one to another when amenities are located within walking or biking distance of residential spaces and other settings), promote social inclusion, and increase the likelihood of people meeting and socially interacting (Song et al., 2013; Zock et al., 2018; Xu, 2019).

We developed an open-source software framework to calculate accessible amenities using various spatial accessibility approaches. First, we specify children's homes or school locations as origins, and a target amenity is then considered accessible if it is either located within a

specified circular buffer (i.e., Euclidean buffer approach) or within a specified walking distance (i.e., pedestrian walkshed approach). The results are stored in the form of a comma-separated values (CSV) file. The following sections go into greater detail about our framework's main input and output parameters.

4.4.1 Euclidean buffers

Three input parameters need to be defined to calculate which amenities are within a certain Euclidean distance of a given setting (e.g., home or school). The first is about the type of amenities. We look for amenities using both the primary OSM tags (e.g., amenity, leisure, sport) and the more specific OSM categories (e.g., amenity=library, leisure=playground, sport=basketball). The second input parameter is the location used to assess the level of accessibility. The third parameter is the Euclidean distance (in metres) that an amenity is considered accessible within. This process produces a JSON file containing all the information about accessible amenities.

4.4.2 Pedestrian walksheds

We use three main steps to calculate accessible amenities based on network walking distances from a given origin: (1) calculating the pedestrian walkshed (as described in Section 5.3.2), (2) collecting amenities such as playgrounds from OSM, and (3) identifying all amenities located within the pedestrian walkshed. We use the three pedestrian walksheds mentioned in Section 4.3.2 (i.e., 300m, 500m, and 800m network radii, corresponding to 5, 10, and 15-minute walking trips, respectively) to measure access to amenities. This method can be applied to any cohort and school study in Equal-Life. In particular, the geo-coordinates of each cohort and school study can be overlaid with pedestrian walksheds to determine which areas have access to an amenity within a 5, 10, or 15-minute walking trip.

4.4.3 Co-accessibility index

Amenities are places at which individuals of different ages can engage in activities and socialize with one another (Oldenburg, 1999). Moreover, easy access to amenities encourages their use and differences in access capacity (e.g., between children, adults, and the elderly) affect the likelihood of intergenerational encounters. Estimates of the degree to which different age groups have access to the same amenities could approximate how people of different ages occupy the same location and, as a result, serve as a proxy for potential encounters and intergenerational interactions. For this, we enrich our estimated accessibility measures with a number of age-related variables and move from accessibility to co-accessibility (i.e., how accessible a given location is to people of different age groups).

To calculate the co-accessibility index, we first estimate which amenities are accessible to each individual within the three considered pedestrian walksheds (i.e. via the street network) (see Sect. 4.4.2). Next, for each amenity, we calculate the following indicators.

- The total number of people who have access to it.
- The number of people who have access to it per age group. As suggested in (Hagestad and Uhlenberg, 2005), instead of accounting for a single age group (e.g. children) relative to all others, we consider three main age categories that represent the different walks of life (i.e. children, adolescents and adults, and the elderly).

- The age diversity of the people who have access to it by means of Shannon's Equitability Index is given by the following formula: $\frac{-\sum(P_i * \ln P_i)}{\ln(k)}$, where P_i denotes the proportion of each age category i relative to the total number of people who have access to a given location, and k is the number of age categories.

Following these steps, we calculate an age-adjusted set of co-accessibility demographics for each amenity included in the study areas. The estimated age-adjusted co-accessibility demographics allow us to determine how accessible each amenity is to different age groups. Fig. 7 depicts the percentages of children and elderly populations among all the people who have access to each amenity location in the five largest cities in the Netherlands (i.e., Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague, Utrecht, and Eindhoven). Fig. 8 depicts the age diversity of the people who have access to each amenity location in the same cities. Our findings suggest that the location of the destinations influences the likelihood of an individual being exposed to people of different ages when visiting them. In addition, according to our findings, the time required to reach a destination influences the co-accessibility and age diversity scores. Destinations within a 10 or 15-minute walk of people's homes, in particular, have higher age diversity scores than destinations within a 5-minute walk of people's homes (i.e., accessible to a lower number of people). This also suggests that encouraging people to limit their activities to a 5-minute walking radius may reduce their chances of meeting people of different ages.

4.4.4 Examples

Figure 7. Amenities in the five largest Dutch cities are classified according to the percentage of children and the elderly who can access each location relative to all other groups within two different walking distances (5 and 15-minute walksheds).

Figure 8. Amenity locations are classified according to the age diversity of the people who have access to them within a 5, 10, or 15-minute walk in the five largest Dutch cities. Shannon's Equitability Index was used to calculate age diversity. Each location's age diversity score ranges from 0% (only one age group has access to such amenities) to 100%. (an equal number of people from each age group have access to such amenities).

4.4.5 Guidelines

- **Data**
 - **Geo-coordinates:** Start with a data set of geo-coordinates for which you want to calculate whether they have access to amenities, for example home or school locations in a cohort or school study data set.
 - **Amenities:** Obtain a dataset of the amenities you want to quantify access to (e.g., playgrounds, sports or health facilities), for example from [OpenStreetMap](#).
 - **Street network:** Optionally, if you want to calculate walksheds or co-accessibility, obtain an urban street network dataset as a connected graph, for example from [OpenStreetMap](#) via the [OSMnx](#) library.
 - **Population:** Optionally, if you want to calculate co-accessibility, obtain a dataset of population statistics, i.e., per neighbourhood, postal code area, or local grid cell (e.g., local data such as by the [Dutch CBS](#)).
- **Process**
 - Generate circular buffer zones around the amenities and determine for every geo-coordinate if it lies within the zone (i.e., it has access) or not.
 - If you have street network data, generate pedestrian walksheds around the amenities and determine for every geo-coordinate if it lies within the zone (i.e., it has access) or not.
 - If you have population and street network data, generate walksheds around the population data (e.g., grid cells centroids) and determine which populations have access to which amenities. Then, for each amenity aggregate the demographic information of all the people (i.e., populations) who have access to it (i.e., their co-accessibility). You can aggregate based on absolute numbers, percentages or using a diversity index as described in Sect. 5.4.3.
- **Software**
 - We use Python code to collect [OpenStreetMap](#) data, and to calculate access. Our code uses, among others, the [OSMnx](#) library (Boeing, 2017) and the [Overpass API](#) for [OpenStreetMap](#). Detailed instructions for installing and running the code for these metrics appear in Sect. 4.2.3 and 4.2.4 of Deliverable 5.8.

4.5 Access to greenspaces³

Exposure to outdoor greenness has been associated with a positive impact on physical health and cognitive development, especially among children (Dadvand et al., 2015). Parks and other outdoor greenspaces provide important venues that promote physical activity (e.g., walking and biking), thereby contributing to a decreased risk of developing obesity and other related chronic diseases (e.g., high cholesterol or blood pressure) (Coombes et al., 2010; Sugiyama et al., 2010). A growing body of literature demonstrates the importance of greenspace use in maximising exposure over other determinants such as the percentage of greenness in an area (Coombes et al., 2010; Labib et al., 2020; Sugiyama et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2011). Greenspace use primarily manifests itself in two ways. First, by making *routine purposeful visits* to greenspaces for leisure or physical exercise (Almanza et al., 2012; Rao et al., 2007; van den

³ This section's content is based on the TUD team's paper "Measuring children's and adolescents' accessibility to greenspaces from different locations and commuting settings" (Teeuwen, Psyllidis & Bozzon, 2023), which measures greenspace accessibility to children and adolescents from their homes, their educational environments, and while commuting between them.

Berg et al., 2016). Second, in the form of *regular traverse movement* through greenspaces, which involves serendipitous walking when commuting to school, work or other activities (Dadvand et al., 2015; Roberts & Helbich, 2021; Zijlema et al., 2018).

Evidence suggests that greenspace use is primarily encouraged by accessibility (Zhang, et al., 2021). Specifically, easy access emerges as the main motivating factor in studies investigating what encourages people to visit a greenspace such as a park (Talal & Santelmann, 2021). Thus, measuring access to greenspaces is critical for evaluating the degree of use and its corresponding impact on health outcomes.

In line with the European common indicator for greenspace and the definition of urban greenspace by the World Health Organization⁴, we consider vegetated spaces within the city of at least 0.5 hectares in size (Ambiente Italia, 2003; World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe, 2017). We exclude areas for crop production, as these are typically not publicly accessible. Another option is to consider only greenspaces of the type of *park*: a public space typically specifically designed for human leisure activities, such as sports, meetings with friends and others, and relaxation. We select only those greenspaces or parks that intersect with the pedestrian road network: that is, those that are publicly accessible on foot.

Access to urban greenspaces is typically calculated on the basis of Euclidean distances (i.e., circular buffer zones) or on the basis of the existing pedestrian road network (i.e., walksheds). In addition, we have explored the potential of using *betweenness* accessibility measures to quantify access to greenspaces while *on the move* (i.e., during regular traverse movement, such as children's and adolescents' daily commutes from home to educational facilities). Below, we describe calculations of greenspace accessibility based on Euclidean buffers, pedestrian walksheds, and on-the-move measures.

4.5.1 Euclidean buffers

The same principles as for calculating Euclidean distance access to amenities can be applied to calculating Euclidean distance access to greenspace. As a result, we refer to section 4.4.1. However, unlike amenities that are typically small in size (e.g., a playground or sports facility), greenspaces are typically of a certain size (i.e., at least 0.5 hectares according to our definition, but with some extending over a square kilometre). Kabisch and Haase (2014) propose creating Euclidean distance zones for greenspace around its *entrance* locations, rather than its centre point or boundaries.

4.5.2 Pedestrian walksheds

Around every greenspace, we generate 300m, 500m, and 800m network radius distance walkshed zones, corresponding to a 5, 10, and 15-minute walking trip. As the greenspaces we consider are of a certain size (i.e., at least 0.5 hectares according to our definition, but with some extending over a square kilometre), we generate the walksheds such that they cover all street segments that are within walking distance from *any intersection* within the greenspace, opposed to solely around the centroid.

Our method can be used to identify what cohort or school study geo-coordinates (either school or home locations) lie within a 300, 500, or 800-metre walk from greenspace, respectively.

⁴ "Urban spaces covered by vegetation of any kind" (World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe, 2017).

Below, we provide three indicative examples of our accessibility analyses for greenspaces of the type of park, covering (parts of) seven different cohorts and school study areas in the cities of Amsterdam, Barcelona, and Gothenburg (Fig. 9). Our method can be replicated for other urban areas with cohort or school study geo-coordinates available within Equal-Life.

Furthermore, we overlay the generated walksheds with a high-granularity population statistics dataset that differentiates between populations of children and populations of adolescents (i.e., the Dutch Central Statistics Agency CBS differentiates between populations of age 0 to 14, and age 15 to 24), and with data sets of educational facilities for children (e.g., primary schools) and for adolescents (e.g., secondary schools, colleges, and universities). By doing so, we can determine to what extent every greenspace in a city is accessible to children and adolescents, respectively, from their homes and from their educational environment. We see that differences emerge between settings and age groups, as well as between greenspaces varying in size and surroundings.

Figure 9. Pedestrian access to parks in (A) Barcelona, Spain; (B) Amsterdam, The Netherlands; and (C) Gothenburg, Sweden.

4.1.3 Access on the move

Freeman (1977) introduced betweenness as the fraction of the shortest paths between any pair of nodes in a network. For example, for a street network, betweenness describes in between how many pairs of intersections a given street segment lies. Sevtsuk (2021) introduced *patronage betweenness* to estimate flows of pedestrians on the move from one location (an *origin*, e.g., their home) to another (a *destination*, e.g., school) while accounting for typical pedestrian behaviour. As such, patronage betweenness is used as an accessibility measure on the assumption that people who pass by a location are more likely to visit it because they do not have to make a separate trip (Sevtsuk, 2020). For greenspaces, this translates into children being exposed to greenspaces on a daily basis, such as while walking from home to school without making a separate trip, as long as their commuting path passes through vegetated areas. This regular exposure may, in turn, result in better health (Dadvand et al., 2015).

We operationalise accessibility to people on the move using patronage betweenness. We first pre-process origins and destinations in Python. As origins, we use residential environments: either home locations of cohort or school study children or residential populations of children or adolescents per grid cell in high-granularity local population statistics datasets if the overall commuting patterns among children in a city are of interest. As destinations, we use locations of educational facilities: the school locations in the cohort or school study data sets, or, again, if the general pattern in a city is of interest, we use a local dataset with the locations of primary schools for children or secondary schools, colleges, and universities for adolescents. Furthermore, for computational efficiency, we pre-process the pedestrian street network via which children or adolescents may commute: we simplify complex intersections while maintaining network topology using the Python OSMnx package.

We then calculate patronage betweenness using the *Urban Network Analysis* toolbox for Rhino (Sevtsuk & Kalvo, 2016; Sevtsuk, 2021). This toolkit uses the following equation:

$$PB[s]^{r,dr} = \sum_{j,k \in G - \{s\}, d[j,k] \leq r \cdot dr} \frac{n_{j,k[s]}}{n_{j,k}} \cdot W[j, k] \frac{1}{e^{\beta \cdot d[j,k]}}$$

For each street segment s , this equation sums over all potential origin and destination pairs j, k , such that s lies on an admissible path between j and k . Paths are admissible when their distance d is no longer than radius r and at maximum a factor dr (detour ratio) longer than the shortest path connecting j and k . Then the equation takes the share of admissible paths between j and k that lead through s , multiplies it with weight factor W based on the supply and demand of commuters at j and k , and accounts for a distance decay effect β .

We consider all pairs of origins and destinations that lie within 800 metres distance from each other (i.e., a 15-minute walk). As pedestrians tend to make detours up to 20% and prefer to walk along parks, we set the detour ratio dr to 1.2 (Sevtsuk, 2020; Salazar Miranda et al., 2020). We apply a distance decay effect (i.e., people are less likely to walk when distance increases) β of 0.002 for short walking commutes (Handy and Niemeier, 1997). We weigh origins by the number of children or adolescents living there (i.e., 1 when using cohort or school study home addresses as origins, or the population count in case of population grid cells as origins). We weigh destinations equally, i.e., 1 for every educational facility.

Doing so, we calculate an estimated number of children or adolescents commuting through every street segment in our street network dataset, assuming that they walk to any educational facilities within 800 metres from their homes, with higher chances of walking to facilities that are close by. This process results in a heat map of estimated commutes. Fig. 10 shows (A) origin-homes, destination schools, and the street network in between for the Barcelona school study BREATHE, and (B) the outcomes of the patronage betweenness calculation: an estimated heat map of BREATHE children commuting between home (blue) and school (red). Fig. 11 shows an estimated heat map of the overall children’s population commuting between homes (based on population statistics per 100 m grid cell) and all primary schools in the city of Amsterdam, Netherlands.

These data on estimated commutes can help us understand where in the city children may be exposed to vegetation while moving from home to school. Furthermore, we can use them to quantify per greenspace how many children may pass through it on a day-to-day basis.

Future work could use patronage betweenness to capture other exposures in places that are commonly traversed by children, dependent on their activity settings (e.g., their homes, educational facilities, and other routine locations). That is, for example, to assess traffic noise, safety, or air pollution along streets frequented by commuting children.

Figure 10. Estimated commuting flows between homes and schools of children included in the BREATHE school study in Barcelona (800m maximum network radius distance, no detours). (A) input data on children’s homes, schools, and the street network. (B) output data on the estimated number of commuting children per street segment.

Figure 11. Estimated commuting flows between homes and schools of all children in Amsterdam, the Netherlands (800m maximum network radius distance, detours up to 20% longer than the shortest path).

4.5.4 Examples

Fig. 12 depicts how many children or educational facilities can access each greenspace. There are significant differences between the greenspaces depending on how we measure their degree of accessibility (i.e., through walksheds around homes, walksheds around schools, or betweenness measures).

Children's greenspace accessibility

Figure 12. Greenspace accessibility in three exemplary areas in the Netherlands: (A) Amsterdam, (B) Rotterdam, and (C) The Hague. Accessibility is calculated as the extent to which a greenspace (left) is within walking distance (walkshed) of general population homes; is within walking distance (walkshed) of children's homes; is within walking distance (walkshed) of children's schools; and (right) is on the route (betweenness) between children's homes and schools.

4.5.5 Guidelines

- **Data**
 - **Geo-coordinates:** Start with a data set of geo-coordinates for which you want to calculate whether they have access to amenities, for example, home or school locations in a cohort or school study data set.
 - **Greenspaces:** Obtain a dataset of greenspaces, for example from [OpenStreetMap](#).
 - **Street network:** Obtain an urban street network dataset as a connected graph, for example from [OpenStreetMap](#) via the [OSMnx](#) library.
 - **Population:** Optionally, if you want to calculate on-the-move accessibility, obtain a dataset of population statistics, i.e., per neighbourhood, postal code area, or local grid cell (e.g., local data such as by the [Dutch CBS](#)), or houses (e.g., from [OpenStreetMap](#), filtering on building tags).
 - **Educational facilities:** Optionally, if you want to calculate on-the-move accessibility, obtain a dataset of educational facility locations, e.g., schools, colleges, or university buildings (e.g., from local data or [OpenStreetMap](#)).
- **Process**
 - Generate pedestrian walksheds around the greenspaces and determine for every geo-coordinate if it lies within the zone (i.e., it has access) or not. Generate the walksheds around any intersection within a greenspace, as opposed to e.g., around its centroid, to ensure we calculate the zone from where people can enter into the greenspace.
 - If you want to calculate on-the-move accessibility, decide if you want to use geo-coordinates from specific home or school locations, or if you want to use population and educational facility data for an area. For computational efficiency, simplify your street network data set while maintaining topological relations, for example using [OSMnx](#). Calculate patronage betweenness values per segment in your street network, using home locations as origins and school locations as destinations. This process results in a heat map of on-the-move pedestrian activity between homes and schools. Overlay the heat map with the greenspaces to calculate the amount of pedestrian activity estimated to take place within the greenspace: its on-the-move accessibility. Note that the heat map shows pedestrian activity on an aggregate level, and is not meant to be disaggregated to values per single geo-coordinate location.
- **Software**
 - We use Python code to collect [OpenStreetMap](#) data, and to pedestrian walksheds. Our code uses, among others, the [OSMnx](#) library (Boeing, 2017) and the [Overpass API](#) for [OpenStreetMap](#). To calculate patronage betweenness values for access on the move, we use the [Urban Network Analysis toolbox for Rhino](#) (Sevtsuk & Kalvo, 2016; Sevtsuk, 2021). Detailed instructions for installing and running the code for these metrics appear in Sect. 4.2.5 of Deliverable 5.8.

4.6 Access to playgrounds

Having access to playgrounds contributes to children's physical activity and social interactions, which may benefit their physical and mental health (Perez-Del-Pulgar et al, 2021). Children value play spaces that challenge them, with equipment that matches their physique, and where they encounter other children to play and interact with. Furthermore, not only formal playgrounds

may provide children with space to play, but also other types of open space in the city, such as spacious sidewalks and greenspaces (Finney & Atkinson, 2020; McCurdy et al., 2010; Sundevall and Jansson, 2020; Veitch et al., 2007).

In addition to the physical and social benefits of outdoor play in general, *unsupervised* outdoor play contributes to children's self-esteem, motor skills development, independence, and ability to manage risks (Brussoni et al., 2015). While children value playing without supervision (Veitch et al., 2007), the opportunity to do so depends on how parents perceive the play environment in terms of safety: for example, traffic safety, injuries while playing, and incidents involving strangers (Amiour et al., 2022; Carver et al., 2008; Finney & Atkinson, 2020; Qiu & Zhu, 2021; Truong et al., 2022; Veitch et al., 2006).

Access to playgrounds is typically measured by means of Euclidean buffer zone or pedestrian walksheds (i.e., network buffer zones) (see for example, calculations in studies by Perez-Del-Pulgar et al. (2021) and No et al. (2022)). In addition to these measures, we developed a *child's play* accessibility metric that specifically accounts for opportunities to play outdoors *without supervision*. The following paragraphs discuss measuring Euclidean, walkshed, and child's play accessibility to play spaces. We refer to the principles for measuring the width of pedestrian infrastructure in Sect. 4.1.1 for spacious sidewalks directly outside children's residences as a place for play.

4.6.1 Euclidean buffers

The same principles apply to calculating Euclidean distance access to playgrounds as they do to other types of amenities. Sect. 4.4.1 contains additional information.

4.6.2 Pedestrian walksheds

The same principles that apply to other types of amenities can be used to calculate access to playgrounds via pedestrian walksheds. Sect. 4.4.2 contains additional information.

4.6.3 Children's play-space metric⁵

Sometimes, using Euclidean distance buffer zones or pedestrian walksheds does account for the many nuances that come with children accessing space to play, especially when they are without parental supervision. In an iterative co-design process (Sanders & Stappers, 2008), we developed together with 20 European experts on children's health or the built environment a metric that calculates the ease with which children can reach places for play: we refer to this metric as our *child's play* accessibility metric. We organised two co-design sessions. The first was in Utrecht, The Netherlands (with stakeholders working on a project used as a case study of Equal-Life WP4) and one in Milan, Italy (as part of a 2-day Equal-Life stakeholder forum led by Equal-Life WP8). Participants are based in Italy, Slovenia, The Netherlands, Slovakia, Ireland, Estonia, Finland, and Belgium. During the co-design process, we used materials map and street-level imagery data from Utrecht (The Netherlands), Milan (Italy) and Ljubljana (Slovenia). Participants commented on elements they recognised in the data that either limit or promote children's accessibility to outdoor play space in these environments, while discussing

⁵ This section's content is based on the TUD team's paper "Easy as child's play? Co-designing a network-based metric for children's access to play space" (Teeuwen & Psyllidis, 2023), which introduces a novel co-designed metric to measure the ease with which children can reach play spaces without supervision.

with each other examples from their own personal experience, either from the three cities at hand or from their own home environment elsewhere.

From the co-design process, we identified four main themes of factors that affect children's access to play space:

- **Along the route** from home to the play space, *barriers* may exist that children may not be allowed to cross (e.g., car infrastructure, bus and tram lines, but also large-size greenspaces), even if the play space is close-by (i.e., within roughly 300 metres distance). Yet, if well-designed, the route to play space may also be part of the fun.
- **Destinations**, where children play, include *playgrounds*, other open spaces such as sidewalks and schoolyards, and small greenspaces with an open layout and playful vegetation well-integrated into the neighbourhood fabric.
- **Social interactions** play a key role in urban public space. As such, the culture, social bonds, and perceived safety in a neighbourhood affect the extent to which parents let their children play outdoors. Furthermore, children are attracted to places where others play as well, while conflicts with peers or other user groups may have adverse effects.
- **Unsupervised play** depends on more than just the spatial environment: for example, parenting style, the age and experience of the child, and the cultural context.

Dependent on the nature of the data, some of these factors can be recognised in spatial data (e.g., OpenStreetMaps) while others require local knowledge and field work to take into account: specifically, factors that can be recognised are (1) *barriers along routes* such as main traffic infrastructure and water bodies that cannot safely be crossed via pedestrian tunnels or bridges, and the inner parts of large greenspaces where natural surveillance may be lacking, and (2) the variety of *destinations* for play including *playgrounds*, *schoolyards*, and small-size *greenspaces* (i.e., up to 5 hectares). (For *sidewalks* as play spaces, we refer again to Sect. 4.1.1 on street infrastructure).

Our resulting *child's play* accessibility metric identifies areas where children can walk 300 metres without crossing any barriers to any type of play space. As such, it is an extension of commonly used pedestrian walkshed metrics by accounting not only for proximity but also for barriers, while acknowledging other places where children play beyond formal playgrounds. In Fig. 13, we show the results of implementing our metric (D) in an area in Utrecht, The Netherlands, in comparison to implementing simpler metrics (A, B & C). Our metric is implemented in Python code and based on open data from OpenStreetMap. Upon seeing initial versions of our metric, participants were triggered to reflect on equity issues associated with how children's homes, play spaces, and spatial barriers are distributed over the city. We do stress that while our *child's play* metric provides a more realistic representation of children's access to play spaces in the city compared to other methods (e.g., pedestrian walksheds), *fieldwork* and collecting experiences of *local* communities are necessary to complement the information captured by our metric with all the nuances (e.g., qualities of equipment, social interactions, and cultural context) that contribute to children's opportunities to play outdoors.

4.6.4 Examples

Fig. 13 shows how our *child's play* accessibility metric compares with Euclidean buffer and pedestrian walkshed approaches to measuring accessibility. For an area in Utrecht, The

Netherlands, we show the areas that are considered to have access to play space and calculate the percentage of children that have access to play space for each of the methods visualised: With Euclidean buffers around playgrounds, we estimate 90% of children living in the area have access, opposed to 79% when using pedestrian walksheds. When we take into account that not only playgrounds but also small greenspaces and schoolyards are places for play, we estimate 94% of children have access, which decreases again to 81% of children when we also take barriers into account (i.e., when we use our child's play accessibility metric).

Comparing child's play accessibility to baseline for Utrecht

Figure 13. Calculating accessibility to play spaces in Utrecht, The Netherlands, using (A) Euclidean distance zones around playgrounds, (B) pedestrian walksheds around playgrounds, (C) pedestrian walksheds around a variety of play spaces, and (D) our *child's play* accessibility metric that accounts for both barriers and a variety of play spaces.

4.6.5 Guidelines

- **Data**
 - **Geo-coordinates:** Start with a data set of geo-coordinates for which you want to calculate whether they have access to amenities, for example, home or school locations in a cohort or school study data set.
 - **Playspace destinations:** Obtain a dataset of destinations including playgrounds, schoolyards (including playgrounds on school premises) and small greenspaces (≤ 5 ha.), for example from [OpenStreetMap](#).
 - **Barriers:** Obtain a dataset of barriers including main roads and railway infrastructure, and large greenspaces (> 5 ha.), for example from [OpenStreetMap](#).
 - **Street network:** Obtain an urban street network dataset as a connected graph, with information about segments located on bridges or in tunnels, for example from [OpenStreetMap](#) via the [OSMnx](#) library.
- **Process**
 - For the large greenspaces in the data set of barriers, exclude their outskirts by giving them a negative buffer of 40 metres (i.e., cutting off the outer area where natural surveillance may still be possible).
 - Overlay your street network with barriers. For every street network segment that intersects with a barrier, and that is not located in a bridge or tunnel with pedestrian infrastructure, excluding those segments from your street network: these segments, children may not be allowed to cross without supervision.
 - Using your modified street network data set, generate pedestrian walksheds around the three types of play spaces and determine for every geo-coordinate if it lies within the zone (i.e., it has access) or not. Use a distance of 300 metres for your walksheds: the distance children may be allowed to walk without supervision.
- **Software**
 - We use Python code to collect [OpenStreetMap](#) data and to calculate child's play access. Our code uses, among others, the [OSMnx](#) library (Boeing, 2017) and the [Overpass API](#) for [OpenStreetMap](#). Detailed instructions for installing and running the code for these metrics appear in Sect. 4.2.6 of Deliverable 5.8.

4.7 Perceived attributes of the physical environment

4.7.1 Crowdsourcing perceptions of the built environment

Exposures to the physical environment are influenced by factors other than design and layout. Perceived qualities are also essential in how people experience their surroundings while walking, cycling, or resting. The sections that follow present a set of methodologies for capturing experiential factors of the physical environment that, despite their importance, are rarely considered by any walkability or accessibility scores or related indexes due to their subjective nature, difficulty in quantifying, and limited data availability at larger spatial extents. To the greatest extent possible, we strive to develop reliable and reproducible crowdsourcing methodologies for measuring city-wide perceptions of physical environment features such as perceived safety, “eyes on the street” from surrounding buildings, attractiveness, and perceptions of greenspaces.

4.7.2 Perceived safety⁶

Safe outdoor environments contribute substantially to a neighbourhood's level of livability. A growing body of literature has shown that the design and structure of the physical environment can influence both actual safety risks and how different population groups perceive safety, subsequently impacting citizens' physical and mental health and well-being (Foster and Giles-Corti, 2008; Jackson and Stafford, 2009; Mason et al., 2013; Stafford et al., 2007). Especially in neighbourhoods where the fear of crime is disproportionate to the actual crime rates, there is evidence of significant associations with lower levels of physical activity (e.g., limited play among children and walking in older populations, or women being discouraged from using parts of the neighbourhood), leading to increased levels of childhood obesity and social isolation amongst the elderly (Barnett et al., 2017; Groshong et al., 2020; Won et al., 2016).

A common denominator across theories and design approaches aimed at improving actual and perceived safety is the provision of natural (or passive) surveillance in urban public spaces (Crowe, 2000). Originating in what Jane Jacobs referred to as "eyes on the street" (Jacobs, 1961), enhancing a neighbourhood's level of *natural surveillance* has become a widely adopted design guideline towards safer urban environments (Carmona, 2021; UN-Habitat, 2020). Natural surveillance is a by-product of how citizens normally and routinely use public spaces (Crowe, 2000). Even though there are several factors that can influence the level of natural surveillance, it is generally assumed that characteristics such as good street lighting, an abundance of unobstructed windows overlooking walkways, and more permeable streets contribute to an increased level of natural surveillance (Cozens, 2015; Foster et al., 2011). Several approaches to measuring natural surveillance have been proposed to date, ranging from collecting observations on the ground (Lee et al., 2017; Peeters and Vander Beken, 2017; Reynald and Elffers, 2009) to computational models for estimating sightlines (Amiri and Crain, 2020; Shach-Pinsly, 2019). Yet, measurements across large spatial extents remain challenging even for computational approaches, primarily due to the subjective nature of surveillance and the lack of relevant fine-grained data.

We developed a method for measuring natural surveillance at scale using street-level imagery and computer vision techniques. Unlike related approaches that use generic proxies of visibility such as the distance between buildings (De Nadai et al., 2020; Shach-Pinsly, 2019), street-level imagery gives us the opportunity to capture built-environment features that can affect natural surveillance, such as the location of windows on a building facade and any visibility blockages by fences or vegetation.

We extract these features with geolocalization and computer vision (i.e., facade labelling) techniques. We calculate sightlines from the windows to each street and vice versa, as well as the windows of surrounding buildings, using the extracted features. Drawing on the work of (Peeters and Vander Beken, 2017) and (Amiri and Crain, 2020), we calculate two types of surveillance for each street segment: (1) *street surveillance*, which captures the surveillance of windows from the street level and vice versa, and (2) *occupant surveillance*, which captures the surveillance of windows from surrounding buildings.

⁶ This section's content is based on the TUD team's paper "Eyes on the street": Estimating natural surveillance along Amsterdam's city streets using street-level imagery" (van Asten, Miliás et al., 2023), which discusses how natural surveillance can be measured and its relationship to perceived safety in greater detail.

We estimate natural surveillance at the street-segment level considering both *street* and *occupant* surveillance. Both of these surveillance types depend on the degree to which people are able to observe the street from a specified distance; what is usually referred to as a *sightline*. We group sightlines according to three parameters. The first parameter is based on the assumption that surveillance from ground-floor windows is associated with lower levels of street crime than surveillance from upper-floor windows, which is supported by previous research (Lee et al., 2017). We group sightlines based on their altitude a_{max} to study the impact surveillance from different window levels has on street safety. Assuming that each building story is approximately $3m$ high, the value of a_{max} for first-floor windows is $3m$, for first and second-floor windows it is $6m$, and for first, second, and third-floor windows it is $9m$. Second, existing literature indicates that the most reliable distance to observe and interpret an event is $15m$ (Amiri and Crain, 2020; Jong et al., 2005; Lindsay et al., 2008). Furthermore, events witnessed from a $43m$ distance produce weak but reliable eyewitness accounts. Therefore, we divide sightlines into two types: those with $d_{max} \leq 15m$ and those with $d_{max} \leq 43m$. Finally, we define an angle θ_{fov} as the field of view visible through a window. Outside of this field of view, sightlines are excluded.

Detection and geolocalization of windows. The first step in the calculation of sightlines is the detection of windows on building facades along streets. We collect street-level imagery along the streets of interest and detect windows using the facade labelling algorithm developed by (Li et al., 2020). The algorithm detects four key points (i.e., top-left, bottom-left, bottom-right, and top-right) using 2D heatmaps. Then, it links them together using a neural network trained on labelled images with varying facade structures, viewing angles, lighting, and occlusion conditions. Following this, we calculate the geolocation of each detected window by using and adapting the geolocalization algorithm that was originally developed by (Qiu et al., 2019) and later modified by (Sharifi Noorian et al., 2020). For each of the detected windows, this process calculates the latitude, longitude, and altitude of the four key points in the street-level images (Fig. 14). We then compute the centre point and store it as the window's geolocation.

Figure 14. Indicative outputs of the facade labelling algorithm developed by (Li et al., 2020) on street-level images collected in Amsterdam.

Street and occupant surveillance. To calculate street surveillance, we count all sightlines that have as a starting point the windows with an altitude lower than a_{max} and as an endpoint the

location of the street-car camera, with a length lower than d_{max} . The number of these sightlines reflects the number of windows with unobstructed views to points sampled across the street network (i.e., every 10m). Regarding occupant surveillance, we calculate for each window the number of neighbouring windows with an unobstructed view (i.e., sightline). Specifically, for each detected window $o_{viewpoint}$ with an altitude lower than $amax$, we select all neighbouring windows that have an altitude lower than $amax$ and are at a maximum distance d_{max} from each $o_{viewpoint}$.

Next, we calculate all sightlines from the neighbouring windows to the $o_{viewpoint}$ and remove the ones obstructed by intermediate buildings. In particular, for each sightline s , we calculate the angle θ_s between s and the building segment that contains $o_{viewpoint}$. If $\theta_s > 1 \theta_{fov}$, we consider s outside the field of view of the neighbouring window and remove it from the set of sightlines to be considered. Due to the restriction of the sightline angle, a sightline originating from each window ($o_{viewpoint}$) to each neighbouring window ($o_{neighbor}$) does not imply that the reverse also exists. By repeating these steps for each detected window, we calculate how many neighbouring windows have unobstructed views of each window at hand.

To calculate the overall natural surveillance scores, we link all points with a street and occupant surveillance score to a given street segment q . We define a street segment as a section of the street between two junctions, or between a junction and the end of the street if the street has a dead end. More specifically, each window is linked to the image where it was detected, and this is, in turn, linked to the corresponding street segment. We calculate the following two scores, normalised by the street segment's length:

$$S_q = \frac{1}{q_L} \sum_{s \in S_q} s_i$$

$$O_q = \frac{1}{q_L} \sum_{o \in O_q} o_i$$

where S_q and O_q respectively denote the set of street and occupant sightlines linked to a street segment q , q_L is the length of street segment q in metres, and s_i and o_i denote the number of sightlines observing points s and o , respectively.

We further aggregate our scores at the neighbourhood level by calculating the sum of the sightlines of all points within each neighbourhood and dividing it by the length of each street segment using the following formulas:

$$S_q = \frac{\sum_{s \in S_n} s_i}{\sum_{q \in Q_n} q_L}$$

$$O_q = \frac{\sum_{o \in O_n} o_i}{\sum_{q \in Q_n} q_L}$$

where S_q^n and O_q^n respectively denote the sum of street and occupant sightlines within a neighbourhood n with street segments q , and Q_n is the set of sampled street segments within n . As previously stated, we further group our scores according to whether the distance between the windows and the corresponding street segment is reliable for witnessing an event ($d_{max} = 15m$) or dependable ($d_{max} = 43m$).

Fig. 15 depicts an example of our methodology being used in an area covering 40 districts in the city of Amsterdam. Scores for street and occupant surveillance are aggregated at the street and neighbourhood levels. If street-level imagery is available, our methodology can be replicated in other areas covered by the Equal-Life cohorts and school studies.

Figure 15. (A) street surveillance scores, (B) occupant surveillance scores covering 40 districts in the city of Amsterdam classified into tertiles (Green: High; White: Medium; Red: Low).

4.7.3 Perceived attractiveness⁷

Attractive and safe public spaces are essential to a city's vibrancy, as they encourage social interaction and physical activity through walking and cycling (Anderson et al., 2017; Stevenson et al., 2016; Alfonzo, 2005). Since streets account for the majority of public space in cities, a

⁷ This section's content is based on the TUD team's paper "Is it safe to be attractive? Disentangling the influence of streetscape features on the perceived safety and attractiveness of city streets" (Milias et al., 2023), which discusses how to capture perceived attributes of the urban environment.

growing body of literature focuses on identifying street design features that encourage active travel while also improving people's experiences and well-being (Harvey et al., 2015; Whyte, 2012; Adkins et al., 2012; Ewing and Handy, 2009; Mehta, 2009). Greenery, the density and mix of land uses along streets, the morphology and aesthetics of buildings, intersection density, good visibility and street lighting, and the quality and maintenance of sidewalks have been identified as essential characteristics of safe and walkable streets (Basu and Sevtsuk, 2022; Park and Garcia, 2020; Sallis et al., 2020; Ding and Gebel, 2012; Rydin et al., 2012; Ewing and Handy, 2009). However, the subjective nature of perception, as well as the variety of conditions that influence it, makes determining these issues particularly difficult. Place perceptions vary among people of different ages, income levels, ethnic backgrounds, physical abilities, or past experiences (Barnett et al., 2017; Candeia et al., 2017; Cao, 2016; Traunmueller et al., 2015; Jim and Shan, 2013; Won et al., 2016), and getting a representative sample of people to participate in city-scale studies takes time and effort.

We created a crowdsourcing tool (Fig. 16) that uses street-level imagery to determine how different design features contribute to a street's overall sense of safety and attractiveness. Crowdsourcing was chosen as a time- and labour-efficient practice that allows us to recruit participants at scale while controlling for demographic characteristics such as age, gender, or country of residence. Street-level images are chosen because most streetscape characteristics can be seen visually and are thus depicted in such images (e.g., the number of shops and trees, the width of the street, and the number of cars).

The developed tool integrates three key characteristics. (1) City streets are depicted as a sequence of panoramic (360) street-level images. In this way, we can study how participants' perceptions develop along the street and investigate to what degree the characteristics participants encounter along a street influence how they perceive it. Participants have complete control over their experience and can explore the streets at their own pace. They can digitally traverse the streets (by moving from one image to another), turn their view, and zoom in and out. (3) The tool asks the participants to traverse a path (consisting of multiple streets) and to rate locations along the path according to two questions: "how safe is this place in your opinion?" and "how attractive is this place in your opinion?". Moreover, the tool prompts the participants to explain their ratings further. This input can be used to capture what are the main characteristics that influence the participants' rating process.

Based on our tool we captured street features that influence how safe and attractive streets are perceived for 27 paths (500-750m each), each path consisting of multiple streets, covering areas in the centre and outskirts of Frankfurt, Germany (Fig. 17). Our findings suggest that the features that contribute to a street's perceived safety do not always overlap with those that contribute to its attractiveness, and vice versa. The number of people and parked cars, the volume of traffic, and the presence of graffiti all have an impact on the feeling of safety. In turn, the presence of greenery, as well as the number and type of amenities along a street, are the primary contributors to the attractiveness of a street. We also provide evidence that certain characteristics, such as underpasses and construction sites, have a negative impact on both the perceived safety and attractiveness of city streets, outweighing the influence of any other set of characteristics. This work presents an interesting future research direction in the measurement of urban design qualities, which can be incorporated into evidence-informed design standards for safer and more attractive cities that promote health and well-being.

Figure 16. *Top:* The user interface of the crowdsourcing tool for capturing how safe and attractive city streets are perceived. *Bottom left:* A bird-view map example after two locations have been rated (marked with a star) and nine locations have been visited (green points). *Bottom right:* A pane example in which participants provide their input to explain their ratings.

Figure 17. An indicative example of the perceived safety and attractiveness ratings of 37 locations along a path located in the Bornheim/Ostend district of Frankfurt, Germany.

4.7.4 Perceptions of greenspaces

Urban greenspaces have positive effects on people’s health in multiple ways. While the availability of greenspaces can help reduce heat stress and air pollution, visiting them can encourage healthy activities such as physical exercise, relaxation, and social interaction with other people (Zhang et al., 2021; Markevych et al., 2017; Van den Berg et al., 2016; Kruize et al., 2020).

Three types of data sources are commonly used to study exposure to greenspace: (1) self-reported subjective perceptions and visits to greenspace in questionnaires, (2) land cover maps such as Urban Atlas and OpenStreetMap, and (3) Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) maps from satellite imagery (Labib et al., 2020; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2017; Lu, 2019; Markevych et al., 2017). The main advantage of land cover and NDVI maps is that they are often openly available at frequent intervals for large areas (i.e., the whole of Europe or even

worldwide). As a result, they are not only used to study health mechanisms but also to assess how healthy cities are and to plan for urban health interventions (Larkin and Hystad, 2019; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2017; Markevych et al., 2017). When it comes to perception and visitation, however, questionnaire data is crucial (Flowers et al., 2016; Fongar et al., 2019).

Using a crowd-sourcing questionnaire, we collect people's perceptions of various greenspaces and planned activity visits in European cities. Fig. 18 depicts a preliminary and indicative example of our crowd-sourcing campaign. With this information, we can learn how well NDVI and land cover maps reflect what people think about greenspaces and what distinguishes the areas where they differ. As a result, we support the interpretation of the collective body of evidence on the relationship between greenspace and health derived from various types of greenspace data sources, in order to better inform urban health intervention planning.

Figure 18. Impression of the crowd-sourced survey on perceptions of greenspace using (A) panoramic street-level imagery of locations in European cities and (B) questions about its perceived vegetation and intended use.

4.7.5 Guidelines

- **Data**
 - **Geo-coordinates:** Begin with a dataset of geo-coordinates that you want to capture perceived qualities for (e.g., how safe people feel these places are).
- **Process**
 - We introduce two approaches for capturing perceived qualities of the urban environment on a city-wide scale.
 - **Using a proxy.** Instead of capturing the perceived quality of your interest, estimate a proxy that correlates with it. For instance, in Section 4.7.2 we introduce street and occupant surveillance scores that can be used to estimate perceived safety along city streets.
 - **Using crowdsourcing.** Recruit participants through a crowdsourcing platform such as [Prolific](#). Show street level images to the participants and ask them how they perceive them.
- **Software**
 - Detailed instructions for installing and running the code for these metrics appear in Sect. 4.2.7 of Deliverable 5.8.

5. Conclusion

This document presented a number of methodologies for measuring physical environment features that have been shown to have the greatest impact on human health, both physical and mental. The metrics that comprise the Data Collection and Enrichment tool were either created from scratch or extended from existing ones to capture the wide range of physical environment characteristics in a scalable manner. In order for cities to achieve their public health and sustainability goals, quantifiable targets and standards must be developed and consistently measured. This unique set of methodologies provides a comprehensive and consistent way of measuring physical environment features that combine design and layout factors with the perceived qualities of a place across different geographical contexts. To ensure comparability and facilitate the adoption of our tool within and outside of Equal-Life, each measurement methodology included in the tool comes with open-source code detailed in Deliverable 5.8. Some of the metrics introduced in this document are proxies and not based on actual, observed measurements (e.g., access on the move and the co-accessibility index are based on modelled estimates of people's flows, rather than observed mobility records). However, it has been demonstrated in related literature that these proxies adequately predict actual pedestrian flows, and have the added benefit of being able to be calculated at a granular level for large spatial extents (e.g., for each street segment and for several cities simultaneously).

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